

The Influence of Religiosity on Premarital Sexual Behavior of Adolescents in Tanjungbalai

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Abstract— Adolescence is a transition period from children to adults that experiences a lot of change, including the maturity of sexual organs. It can make the sexual drive in adolescents. The inability of adolescents to pursue healthy sexual behavior in responding to sexual impulses allows adolescents to engage with premarital sexual behavior. Many factors influence the premarital sexual behavior of adolescents, including religiosity. This research has the objectives to investigate whether there is an influence of religiosity on premarital sexual behavior. Sampling technique is purposive sampling, with 347 subjects range from 15-18 years old and had or were dating. The measurement tools used are premarital sexual behavior scale and religiosity scale. The results of research data analysis are that there is an effect of religiosity on premarital sexual behavior of adolescents. Religiosity tends to reduce premarital sexual behavior.

Keywords— Premarital sexual behavior, religiosity, adolescents.

I. INTRODUCTION

Unhealthy sexual behavior among adolescents, especially unmarried adolescents tends to increase (Chotimah, 2015). This phenomenon is known as premarital sexual behavior. An increase in adolescent attention to sexual life is influenced by physical changes during that period. Maturity of sexual organs and hormonal changes, resulting in the emergence of sexual urges in adolescents. The inability of adolescents to strive for healthy sexual behavior in responding to sexual impulses experienced, allows adolescents to engage with premarital sexual behavior (Setiawan and Nurhidayah, 2008).

Premarital sexual behavior by adolescents can have several adverse effects. The psychological impact caused by feeling guilty or feeling guilty, remorse, low self-respect, negative emotions associated with unwanted pregnancy, as well as carrying out an act of abortion (Soetjijingsih, 2008). In addition to psychological effects, premarital sexual behavior is also at high risk of damage to sexual organs, vulnerable to sexually transmitted diseases such as HIV / AIDS, gonorrhea, genital herpes, syphilis, and chylamindia (Nenggala, 2006).

Premarital sexual behavior by adolescents can be influenced by various things, one of which is religiosity (Kurby, 2007). Religiosity is the overall function of the individual's soul which includes beliefs, feelings, and behaviors that are directed consciously and seriously on the teachings of his religion (Glock and Stark, 1968). Glock and Stark (1968) divided religiosity into five dimensions, namely the ideological dimension, the ritualistic dimension, the experiential dimension, the intellectual dimension, and the consequence dimension

Religious values believed by adolescents can reduce adolescents in premarital sexual behavior, so sexual behavior is carried out in accordance with religious values that are

believed (Jalaluddin, 2008). When a person have good religiosity, he will have strong faith and piety in controlling desires that are contrary to religious norms (Rosidah, 2012).

Tanjungbalai is a town located in North Sumatra which before its territory was expanded from 199 ha (2 km²) to 60.52 km² was once the most populous city in Southeast Asia. The results of researchers' interviews with counseling teacher in one of the high schools in Tanjungbalai found that there were many students who were already dating. Adolescents can freely mingle with the opposite sex, in fact it is not uncommon to see teenagers embracing each other intimately in public places regardless of the surrounding community.

Based on the above explanation, researchers are interested in investigating whether there is an influence of religiosity on premarital sexual behavior in adolescents in Tanjungbalai.

Premarital Sexual Behavior

Sarwono (2011) defines premarital sexual behavior as all behavior that is driven by the sexual desires whether done alone, with the opposite sex, or same-sex without any marriage ties according to religion and can cause psychological consequences for those who do so, namely in the form of mental tension and confusion over social roles that suddenly change.

Kinsey (1998) divides sexual behavior into 4 stages and the higher stages will be preceded by the previous stages. The stages of sexual behavior include:

a. Touching

Stages of contact begin with holding hands until embracing. Holding hands is a form of affection statement over feelings of love in the form of touch.

b. Kissing

Kissing behavior starts from short kissing to kissing using the partner's tongue (deep kissing).

c. Petting

Sexual stages include touching or touching sensitive parts of a partner's body with the aim of arousing sexual arousal. Feeling or holding sensitive body parts of sexual stimulation (erogenous), such as breasts, neck, upper thighs, vagina, penis, and buttocks.

d. Having sex (sexual intercourse)

The stages of sex include intercourse or genital contact.

Religiosity

Religiosity according to Glock and Stark (1968) is the level of one's conception of religion and the level of one's commitment to his religion. The level of conceptualization is the level of one's knowledge of his religion, while the level of commitment is something that needs to be understood as a

whole, so there are various ways for individuals to become religious

The division of dimensions of religiosity according to Glock and Stark (1968) consists of five dimensions, namely the ideological dimension, the ritualistic dimension, the experiential dimension, the intellectual dimension, and the consequence dimension.

II. OBJECTIVES & METHODS

This research has the objectives to investigate whether there is an influence of religiosity on premarital sexual behavior of adolescents in Tanjungbalai. This study uses a scale in gathering data. The scale of premarital sexual behavior is arranged based on the stages of premarital sexual behavior. Participants in this study were 347 of adolescents in Tanjungbalai with criteria had or were dating.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Result

The hypothesis in this research is that there is an influence of religiosity on premarital sexual behavior in adolescents in Tanjungbalai. The results of data processing using regression analysis of the variable religiosity towards premarital sexual behavior obtained a correlation coefficient (r) -.523 sig value .000 (p<.05) and effective contribution by 27.4 % while the remaining 72.6% was caused by the other factors outside this research.

TABEL 1. Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F	Sig.
1	.523	.274	.271	129.916	0.000

Further analysis will look at the similarity of the regression line between religiosity and premarital sexual behavior, which can be seen from the following table:

TABEL 2. Coefficient Correlation

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	129.759	6.782		19.132	.000
Religiosity	-.779	.068	-.523	-11.398	.000

Based on the above table, beta religiosity is obtained of -.523 with t of -11.398 and a significance value of .000 <.005. This shows that religiosity has a significant effect on premarital sexual behavior. The influence that religiosity has on premarital sexual behavior is a negative direction. This shows that religiosity tends to reduce premarital sexual behavior.

Discussion

The results showed that there was an influence between religiosity and premarital sexual behavior, with a significance

value of p <. 001. This shows that religiosity tends to reduce premarital sexual behavior. These results are consistent with the statement expressed by Hawdon and Rothwell (2008) that religiosity is a protective factor that can limit deviant behavior, one of which is risky sexual behavior. Research conducted by Khairunnisa (2013) also found that there was a negative relationship between religiosity and self-control with premarital sexual behavior. Behavior that is governed by religious demands will direct someone in controlling themselves (Khairunnisa, 2013).

The effective contribution of the variable of religiosity in influencing premarital sexual behavior amounted to 27.4%, while the remaining 72.6% was caused by other factors outside this study. Kurby (2007) identifies factors that influence premarital sexual behavior into two categories, namely individual factors and contextual factors. Individual factors include attitude, age, race, or ethnicity and religion, while contextual factors include peers and family.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the research that has been done, it can be concluded that the results obtained are as follows:

- a. There is a significant influence between religiosity with premarital sexual behavior in adolescents. Religiosity tends to reduce premarital sexual behavior.
- b. Religiosity made an effective contribution in influencing premarital sexual behavior by 27.4%, while the remaining 72.6% was caused by other factors outside this study.

V. SUGGESTION

This study research found a negative influence between religiosity and premarital sexual behavior, so it is expected that adolescents can deepen understanding, knowledge, appreciation, carry out religious practices, and internalize values in religion so as to fortify themselves from premarital sexual behavior

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